

Table 1: Frequency distribution of quality assessment scores (Q1–Q11) with average Likert score.

Score	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11
0	4	0	0	0	4	19	0	0	6	0	0
1	0	0	1	2	3	3	3	1	4	1	0
2	1	0	1	6	7	3	4	7	13	1	1
3	4	1	13	6	19	0	6	11	18	7	8
4	35	43	29	30	11	19	31	25	3	35	35
Average	3.5	4.0	3.6	3.5	2.7	1.9	3.5	3.4	2.2	3.7	3.8

Table 2: Quality Assessment Questions

ID	Quality Assessment Criterion
QA1	Is the paper based on research (or is it merely a “lessons learned” report based on expert opinion)?
QA2	Is there a clear statement of the aims of the research?
QA3	Is there an adequate description of the context in which the research was carried out?
QA4	Was the research design appropriate to address the aims of the research?
QA5	Was the recruitment strategy appropriate for the aims of the research?
QA6	Was there a control group with which to compare treatments?
QA7	Was the data collected in a way that addressed the research issue?
QA8	Was the data analysis sufficiently rigorous?
QA9	Has the relationship between researcher and participants been considered to an adequate degree?
QA10	Is there a clear statement of findings?
QA11	Is the study of value for research or practice?